

Bridging Large Language Models and Logic Programming

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Abstract—This paper introduces a self-correcting framework¹ that converts natural language queries into executable Prolog code. The core of our approach is an iterative refinement loop that leverages structured error feedback from the SWI-Prolog engine. A key feature is our dynamic temperature scheduling mechanism, where the LLM’s temperature is incrementally increased upon each failed attempt. This injection of adaptive stochasticity forces the model to escape deterministic failure modes and explore a wider solution space. By tightly integrating Prolog’s logic, the system produces formally verifiable outputs, enhancing reasoning reliability in logically complex scenarios. Experimental results demonstrate the framework’s value as a “logical guardrail”. Although a base LLM may achieve higher average accuracy, our method excels in enhancing reliability where formal reasoning is critical. This is highlighted by its ability to recover correct solutions for a significant portion of the cases (9 out of 24) on which a powerful 72B parameter base model failed, showcasing its utility in applications demanding precision and consistency. The system is deployed in a chat interface, lowering barriers for non-experts while improving productivity for experts using logic programming. Its modular, adaptive design establishes a foundation for combining symbolic reasoning with LLMs, supporting the development of more trustworthy AI systems.

Index Terms—LLM, Prolog, framework, Qwen, chatbot, AI, logic programming

I. INTRODUCTION

Logic programming [1], in particular, Prolog [2], is perhaps the most widely recognized symbolic language and an effective paradigm for knowledge representation and problem solving in situations that require symbolic computation, logical reasoning, and the modeling of complex dependencies. However, its technical syntax and declarative paradigm hinder widespread adoption. This paper introduces a framework that leverages Large Language Models (LLMs) to bridge the gap between natural language and Prolog, enabling users to harness the benefits of logic programming without prior expertise in its syntax.

The framework translates natural language problems into executable Prolog code using a pre-trained LLM (i.e., the Qwen family [3]). It employs an iterative refinement loop to systematically handle errors. Each loop begins with an initial prompt to generate a program. The output is then validated in

two stages: first for structural correctness, such as malformed code or missing queries, and then through execution with the SWI-Prolog engine [4]. Failures at either stage trigger a corrective prompt that instructs the LLM to revise its output. A key component of our strategy is dynamic temperature scheduling. With each failed attempt within the refinement loop, the cycle repeats with an incrementally increased LLM temperature. This deliberate injection of randomness is critical for escaping the deterministic failure modes common in LLMs, forcing the model to explore a wider solution space. As our results show, this technique improves success rates compared to fixed-temperature (temperature=0) approaches used in other methods. The process terminates upon successful execution or when a predefined iteration limit is reached, after which the Prolog engine’s output is translated into natural language. This combination of structured feedback and adaptive stochasticity offers a practical method for enhancing the reliability of LLM-generated logic programs. Although previous studies have addressed LLM applications in logic programming, e.g., code completion, logical form translation, and neuro-symbolic reasoning, our work combines those tasks into an end-to-end LLM system with a deep focus on automated error-correction and refinement. As a result of its modular architecture, the system shows potential for generalization to other domains where problems can be decomposed into formal logical steps. While the evaluation focuses on mathematical reasoning as a representative domain, the framework is designed to address a broader class of logic programming problems through its modular architecture, making it suitable for other domains.

The framework serves two distinct user groups. For novices with little to no Prolog experience, it acts as an accessible entry point to logic programming. It addresses the critical issue of trust by not acting as a black box; instead, it presents the generated Prolog code alongside the natural language answer. This transparency makes the reasoning process verifiable and turns the tool into an educational aid, where users can learn by connecting natural language descriptions to their symbolic representations. For experienced Prolog developers, it serves as a productivity tool. It is not intended to replace their expertise, but to augment it by rapidly generating boilerplate code and a first draft of the program. The expert can then verify, debug,

¹The source code is available at: <https://github.com/Pryce22/LLM-Prolog>

and refine this output, accelerating the development process.

II. RELATED WORK

The combination of Large Language Models (LLMs) and logic programming has increasingly been a lively field of research, including numerous studies that address different challenges in this integration, such as code generation or symbolic reasoning. One such contribution is made by Shin et al. [5], who explored the translation of natural language into formal logic. Their contribution inspired the translation component of our approach, in which natural language syntaxes map onto logical syntaxes. Nevertheless, the method proposed in this paper further generalizes this idea by more concretely integrating the translation process into Prolog code generation and execution. This enables it not only to translate natural language into logic, but also to execute and validate the generated Prolog code, thereby providing a more complete solution for logical reasoning.

In program synthesis, prior efforts, e.g., LogiGLUE [6], focused on automating logical reasoning. While this approach also addresses the same goal, it differs from previous work in that it implicitly embeds an error-driven refinement scheme. The generator repeatedly optimizes the generated code based on execution errors and, in conjunction with feedback from the Prolog engine, ensures an updated output. By iteratively refining reasoning accuracy, a particularly important factor for LLMs where even a single error can significantly affect the output, this process demonstrates improved logical reasoning performance.

At this point, neuro-symbolic systems such as NS-CL [7] offered intriguing perspectives by integrating neural and symbolic AI for solving challenging tasks. In contrast, whereas NS-CL focused on general concept learning across various domains, this work is more specific. The automated generation of Prolog code, specifically targeted toward logic programming tasks, is the primary goal. The proposed framework combines the best of both worlds, not merely acting as a solution automation workflow, but also enabling code generation, execution, and error correction.

Moreover, studies such as Yang et al. (2024) [8] explored the task of generating Prolog code from mathematical word problems. They showed that instructing LLMs to extract predicates and generate symbolic formulas rather than relying solely on chain-of-thought reasoning, yields more accurate arithmetic reasoning on the GSM8K benchmark. This work, however, is designed for broader applicability. It addresses a major class of logic programming problems and introduces a natural language interface usable by individuals with no prior knowledge of the domain. Together with the iterative error-refinement procedure, this interface ensures that the generated code is not only functionally correct, but also logically consistent.

A highly relevant framework, Logic-LM, was recently proposed by Pan et al. (2023) [9]. Their approach and ours are based on the core concept of an iterative refinement loop that uses error messages from an external symbolic solver to

correct LLM-generated logical forms. However, our approach differs in two key aspects: scope and refinement strategy.

First, in terms of scope, Logic-LM is presented as a general framework supporting multiple logical formalisms, integrating solvers such as Pyke for logic programming, Prover9 for First-Order Logic, and others. In contrast, our work conducts a focused, in-depth investigation specifically into integration with Prolog, arguably the most prominent logic programming language. This allows us to tailor the refinement process to the specific characteristics and failure modes encountered when interacting with a full featured Prolog engine like SWI-Prolog.

Second, our refinement strategy differs fundamentally in its handling of creativity. Logic-LM’s implementation relies on a deterministic generation process (temperature=0), which we identify as a key limitation, as it can lead to repetitive failure loops. In contrast, our work introduces dynamic temperature scheduling as a core component for logic code generation. Our contribution here is the methodical, incremental increase of temperature after each failed cycle. This controlled injection of randomness forces the model to escape deterministic failures and explore a diverse solution space. As our evaluation demonstrates, this strategy yields significant performance improvements over a fixed-temperature baseline, representing a practical advancement for building more robust neuro-symbolic systems tailored for Prolog.

III. PROLOG

Prolog is a powerful logic programming language [1] that excels in the domain of problem solving [2] due to its foundation in formal logic, specifically first-order logic (FOL). Unlike traditional imperative programming languages, Prolog operates on the principles of logic and deduction, where programs are essentially sets of logical facts and rules. This makes it particularly effective for tasks that require reasoning, such as symbolic computation, expert systems, and artificial intelligence. Within the broader field of AI, Prolog remains a significant tool for knowledge representation, automated reasoning, and the development of intelligent systems that require deductive inference.

The ability of Prolog to perform automatic theorem proving and backtracking allows it to find solutions to complex problems by exploring possible deductions step by step. Its syntax and structure directly align with FOL, providing a natural and intuitive formalism for representing knowledge and relationships between entities in a problem space. To create a Prolog program, the problem can be broken down into four components: *Facts*, *Rules*, *Goals*, and *Queries*. These components guide the reasoning process and direct the system towards the desired solution. The mathematical formulation of this process can be described as follows:

$$\text{Prolog Program} = \{\text{Facts, Rules}\} \xrightarrow{\text{Query}} \text{Goal} \quad (1)$$

This structure allows for efficient querying, reasoning, and decision-making processes, where the *Goal* is derived from the combination of *Facts* and *Rules*, and the *Query* is posed

to the system to find a solution based on the logical relationships between them. This makes Prolog ideal for domains where logical reasoning and complex dependencies need to be modeled, such as in AI-driven systems, where clear, deductive reasoning is required.

IV. FRAMEWORK ARCHITECTURE

A. Overview

The framework (Figure 1) comprises three main components: an LLM for code generation and natural language processing, a middleware layer for system orchestration, and a Prolog engine for code execution. This modular design ensures flexibility and allows for the easy substitution of components.

Fig. 1. Framework architecture.

B. Component Details

1) *Large Language Model (LLM)*: The LLM serves as the core intelligence of the framework, responsible for two critical functions. First, it handles natural language to Prolog code generation, translating user input, expressed in natural language, into syntactically correct and semantically meaningful Prolog code, including facts, rules, and queries. Second, it translates the output of Prolog execution back into understandable natural language. The framework is designed to be LLM-agnostic. The implementation utilizes Qwen2.5-Coder-32B-Instruct [10] and Qwen2.5-72B-Instruct [11] due to their advanced capabilities, their high performance and their free access available through Hugging Face API [12].

2) *Middleware Layer*: The middleware layer, implemented in Python, acts as the intermediary between the LLM and the Prolog engine. It receives user input and prepares it for the LLM. It then sends prompts to the LLM via its API and receives the generated output, filtering it to obtain the Prolog code and a query to run it. It passes the generated code to the Prolog engine for execution. This involves managing

the execution environment, handling queries, and retrieving results. All of this is done by implementing a feedback loop with a max of ten iterations to refine the generated code based on errors detected during Prolog execution. Error messages and diagnostic information are fed back to the LLM to guide it towards generating a correct solution and the temperature increases with each iteration of the loop. Lastly, it receives the raw output from the Prolog engine and formulates prompts for the LLM to translate these results into natural language.

3) *Prolog Engine*: The Prolog engine is responsible for executing the generated Prolog code. The framework can be integrated with any standard Prolog engine. This implementation uses SWI-Prolog [4] due to its robustness, extensive libraries, and ease of integration with Python via the `pyswip` library [13].

C. Prompt Engineering Strategy

The prompt engineering strategy consists of two main phases. First, an initial seeding prompt instructs the language model to translate the user’s problem into a complete program explicitly structured with facts, rules, and a single query. The template for this initial prompt is shown in Figure 2.

Prompt: “Think of yourself as a Prolog expert, provide a valid Prolog program to solve this problem.
Steps:
 1. Define Facts.
 2. Define Rules.
 3. Define a single Query that uses the rules and facts in this format: `?- Query().`”

Fig. 2. The initial seeding prompt template used to guide the LLM.

At this point, an iterative refinement loop begins, which uses a single corrective prompt template triggered whenever the generated code fails validation due to structural issues (e.g., malformed code) or logical errors. The model is then guided to review and fix its previous attempt by being provided with the original user problem, the flawed code it generated, and the latest error message from the SWI-Prolog engine. This error feedback is updated dynamically with each validation cycle, ensuring the model always works with the most relevant and recent information to progressively improve the code.

D. Workflow

The overall workflow of the framework is encapsulated by the following formulas. First, the following abbreviations for clarity have been defined:

- **I**: Input to the LLM;
- **Instr**: Instructions provided to the LLM;
- **E**: Errors or corrections from previous iterations;
- **T**: Temperature;
- **Ref**: The refinement function;
- **L**: The LLM function itself;
- **Trans**: The LLM translation function;
- **PE**: Prolog Engine;

- **LLMO**: LLM Output;
- **UO**: User Output.

$$LLMO = \mathcal{L}(Ref(\mathcal{L}(I, Instr, E), T)) \quad (2)$$

$$UO = \mathcal{L}(Trans(PE(LLMO))) \quad (3)$$

These formulas summarize the entire process, from user input to final output: **Input (I)**: The user provides a problem description in natural language. **Prompt Engineering and Code Generation**: The middleware layer crafts a prompt for the LLM (L), incorporating the user input (I) and instructions (Instr) to generate Prolog code. The LLM then generates the corresponding Prolog code. **Iterative Code Refinement**: The generated Prolog code is provided to the Prolog engine (PE) for execution. If errors (E) are detected, the middleware layer communicates these errors to the LLM, which generates an updated version of the code. This process is repeated iteratively (represented by the *Ref* function in the formula), with the number of iterations capped at ten. The parameter T in the formula represents the temperature of the model. **Prolog Code Execution**: The refined Prolog code is executed by the Prolog engine (PE), and the results of this execution are returned. **Result Translation (Trans)**: The results from the Prolog engine (PE) are passed back to the LLM (L) for translation (using the *Trans* function) into natural language. **Output to User (UO)**: Finally, the natural language output (UO) and the Prolog code are presented to the user as the final output.

V. IMPLEMENTATION AND EVALUATION

Building on the previously described architecture, we implemented the system and evaluated its performance on logic-based tasks. This section presents the chatbot application, describes the evaluation methodology, and discusses the results.

A. Chatbot Application

To demonstrate the practical utility of the framework, a chatbot app has been designed. The chatbot offers a web interface (implemented with Flask [14]) that allows the user to communicate using natural language. Although this application presents an example of a specific use case, the underlying functionality of this work is not limited to a chatbot paradigm and can be extended to other use cases in which natural language-based Prolog development is necessary.

B. Evaluation Methodology

The performance was evaluated on 300 questions from the Apple GSM-Symbolic dataset [15], which is based on the OpenAI GSM8K dataset [16]. This enriched benchmark includes a wide range of GSM8K question variants with symbolic templates. To assess performance, we measured the number of correctly answered questions by the models, both with and without the framework.

In addition to accuracy, we also evaluated the readability of the generated Prolog code, using a custom automated scoring metric described in the next subsection.

C. Code Quality Metric

In addition to correctness, the quality of the generated Prolog code was quantitatively assessed using an automated readability score. This metric provides insight into the maintainability and clarity of the code produced by the LLM-powered framework, evaluating how closely it conforms to established programming standards. A custom script was developed to calculate this score on a scale of 0 to 100, where 100 represents perfectly readable code. The script penalizes common stylistic and structural violations, including improper naming conventions for predicates, inconsistent indentation, excessive line length, and the presence of unmarked singleton variables. Furthermore, the script assesses the appropriate use of comments, especially when sensitive control-flow operators like the cut (!) or if-then-else (->) are employed, to ensure the generated logic is not only functional but also understandable. This automated scoring provides a consistent and objective measure of the code’s quality.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The evaluation focused on comparing the performance of base LLMs against our framework-enhanced models, analyzing the impact of temperature scheduling, and investigating the framework’s ability to solve problems where base models fail.

A. Overall Performance Comparison

As shown in Table I, the base models (**Qwen-32B with Prolog (Zero-Shot)** and **Qwen-72B with Prolog (Zero-Shot)**) demonstrated limited performance when generating Prolog code directly, achieving relatively low accuracies of 32.00% and 36.30% respectively. In contrast, the framework-enhanced models showed significant improvements in both accuracy and code quality. The iterative error-handling mechanism was a key contributor to this improvement. By utilizing the error messages from the Prolog engine to revise and regenerate code, the models were able to progressively refine their outputs and reach correct solutions.

Qwen-72B Base (Zero-Shot), when prompted to solve the problems directly in natural language, achieved a high accuracy of 92.00%. This result highlights the impressive reasoning abilities of modern LLMs, but as we will show, their probabilistic nature can lead to subtle logical failures. Our framework is not designed to exceed this high average accuracy, but rather to act as a verifiable and deterministic reasoning path for complex problems where formal correctness is paramount. It addresses the challenge of translating reasoning into executable logic, bridging a critical gap for high-stakes applications.

A compelling result from our evaluation is the relatively strong performance of the **Qwen-32B-Coder Framework with Prolog** model, despite its smaller size. Although the larger **Qwen-72B Framework with Prolog** achieved higher accuracy (63.7% vs. 57.7%) and slightly better code readability (87.1 vs. 86.1), the 32B-Coder model still demonstrated competitive results. We attribute this to the specialized nature of the “Coder” variant, which has been fine-tuned extensively

on source code. This targeted training likely enhances its ability to produce syntactically and semantically coherent code, allowing it to perform nearly on par with a significantly larger model.

TABLE I
OVERALL PERFORMANCE COMPARISON (N=300)

Model	# Correct	Accuracy (%)	Avg. Readability
Qwen-32B with Prolog (Zero-Shot)	96	32.00	86.25
Qwen-72B with Prolog (Zero-Shot)	106	36.30	87.83
Qwen-32B Framework with Prolog	173	57.70	86.10
Qwen-72B Framework with Prolog	191	63.70	87.10
Qwen-72B Base (Zero-Shot)	276	92.00	N/A

B. Impact of Temperature Scheduling on Refinement

To optimize the iterative refinement loop, we investigated the role of the LLM’s temperature. We tested a fixed temperature of 0 against a variable schedule that was incrementally increased upon failure. The results, summarized in Table II, confirm our hypothesis that a dynamic schedule helps the framework escape repetitive error states.

TABLE II
IMPACT OF TEMPERATURE ON QWEN32B FRAMEWORK WITH PROLOG (N=300)

Model with Framework	# Correct	Accuracy (%)	Avg. Readability
Qwen-32B (temp=0)	133	44.30	86.50
Qwen-32B (temp=var)	173	57.70	86.10

The variable temperature strategy yielded an important performance improvement, increasing accuracy by over ten percentage points. This indicates that incrementally raising the temperature is an effective method for breaking deterministic failure loops. By encouraging more diverse syntactic and structural variations, this approach improves the model’s ability to navigate around errors. The average readability score remained stable, suggesting that the increased creativity does not come at the cost of generating less maintainable code.

C. Qualitative Analysis of Reasoning Failures

While Table I shows that the base Qwen-72B model achieves high accuracy in natural language, a more detailed picture emerges when we examine the specific subset of problems where it fails.

Out of three hundred total questions, the **Qwen72B Base (Zero-Shot)** model failed to answer twenty-four correctly. Among these failed cases, as shown in Table III, the framework-enhanced models were able to recover a portion, the **Qwen32B Framework** successfully solved nine of them, while the **Qwen72B Framework** solved six. This demonstrates the system’s effectiveness as a fallback mechanism, recovering correct solutions in cases where the base model’s reasoning fails, especially when translating natural language into logic.

To understand the mechanism behind this advantage, a representative failure case is presented in Table IV. The comparison reveals a common failure mode: the base LLM’s reasoning falters due to a semantic misinterpretation. In contrast, our

TABLE III
NUMBER OF CORRECTLY ANSWERED QUESTIONS BY FRAMEWORK-ENHANCED MODELS ON THE SUBSET OF 24 PROBLEMS THAT THE QWEN-72B BASE (ZERO-SHOT) MODEL FAILED TO SOLVE.

Model with Framework	# Correct Answers
Qwen-32B Framework	9
Qwen-72B Framework	6

approach succeeds by compelling the LLM to decompose the problem into a formal structure. The rigid syntax of Prolog forces the creation of distinct predicates for distinct concepts, acting as a “logic guardrail”. This structural enforcement directly prevents the semantic blending that caused the base model’s logical shortcut, demonstrating how the framework’s value lies in providing a reliable and verifiable reasoning path.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper introduced a novel framework that successfully bridges the gap between natural language and logic programming by automatically generating and executing Prolog code. The core contribution is its robust, self-correcting architecture, which features an iterative refinement loop driven by error feedback from a Prolog engine and a **dynamic temperature scheduling** strategy. This mechanism allows the framework to systematically escape deterministic failure modes and converge on logically sound solutions.

Our evaluation revealed the system’s primary value not as a universal replacement for base LLMs, but as a “logical guardrail”. While a powerful base model like Qwen-72B demonstrated strong general reasoning, it was prone to subtle logical errors. Our approach excelled in these exact scenarios, recovering correct, verifiable solutions for a large portion of the problems the base model failed (e.g., 9 out of 24 cases for the Qwen-32B framework). This highlights its role in enhancing reliability and providing verifiable outputs. The effectiveness derives from guiding the LLM to decompose problems into a formal structure, preventing the semantic misinterpretations that lead to reasoning failures.

The practical implications of this work are twofold. First, by abstracting away syntactic complexity, it democratizes logic programming, making its power accessible to non-experts, as demonstrated by our chatbot application. Second, it presents a tangible methodology for combining the flexibility of LLMs with the rigor of symbolic solvers, offering a path toward more robust and transparent AI systems.

Future work will prioritize validating our framework beyond mathematical reasoning by evaluating it on classic logic programming tasks such as automated planning and knowledge base querying. A key challenge we plan to address is the detection of “silent” logical errors, where code executes without failure but produces incorrect results. We will also explore integrating more sophisticated extensions like Constraint Logic Programming (CLP) and investigate using multi-LLM ensembles to enhance generation stability, further bridging the gap between probabilistic models and verifiable symbolic reasoning.

TABLE IV
DETAILED QUALITATIVE COMPARISON WITH FULL REASONING

Problem Statement	
Isabella and Pavel have 199 minutes to walk to grocery store together. It takes them 19 minutes to get to the corner where the library is. It takes them another 11 minutes to get to the park. It will then take double the combined amount they have spent so far to reach the mall. How much longer do they have to get to grocery store without being late, if they have already wasted 48 minutes to get a coffee before their walk?	
Correct Answer: 61	
Case 1: Qwen-72B-Instruct (Base LLM)	Case 2: Our Framework with Qwen-32B
Model Answer: 0	Framework Answer: 61
Generated Reasoning:	Generated Prolog Code:
<p>1. Calculate the total time spent so far:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time spent getting coffee: 48 minutes - Time spent walking to the corner: 19 minutes - Time spent walking to the park: 11 minutes $48 + 19 + 11 = 78 \text{ minutes}$ <p>2. Calculate the time required to reach the mall:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time to reach the mall is double the combined amount spent so far: $2 \times 78 = 156 \text{ minutes}$ <p>3. Calculate the total time spent by the time they reach the mall:</p> $78 + 156 = 234 \text{ minutes}$ <p>4. Determine if they are already late:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Total time available: 199 minutes - Total time spent: 234 minutes $234 - 199 = 35 \text{ minutes late}$ <p>5. Calculate the remaining time:</p> <p>Since they are already late, they have 0 minutes left.</p>	<pre>total_time(199). coffee_time(48). corner_time(19). park_time(11). total_time_spent_so_far(CT, PT, TSSF) :- TSSF is CT + PT. mall_time(TSSF, MT) :- MT is 2 * TSSF. total_time_spent(CT, PT, MT, TTS) :- total_time_spent_so_far(CT, PT, TSSF), mall_time(TSSF, MT), TTS is TSSF + MT. remaining_time(TT, CFT, TTS, RT) :- TotalTimeSpentWithCoffee is TTS + CFT, RT is TT - TotalTimeSpentWithCoffee. ?- total_time(TotalTime), coffee_time(CoffeeTime), corner_time(CornerTime), park_time(ParkTime), total_time_spent(CornerTime, ParkTime, MallTime, TotalTimeSpent), remaining_time(TotalTime, CoffeeTime, TotalTimeSpent, RemainingTime).</pre>
Analysis	
The reasoning fails at Step 1 by semantically blending "coffee time" and "walking time" into the "combined amount they have spent so far". This initial error invalidates all subsequent calculations.	The framework generates a verbose but logically sound program. The rigid structure of Prolog forces the creation of distinct predicates, preventing the semantic error. Its execution is deterministic and correct.

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